

STUDIES ON THE DEPENDENCE OF OPTICAL ROTATORY POWER ON CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION. PART XXI. THE ROTATORY DISPERSION OF STEREOISOMERIC HYDROXYPHENYLAMINOMETHYLENECAMPHORS AND THEIR ACETYLATED AND BENZOYLATED DERIVATIVES

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Aminophenols (*o*-, *m*- & *p*-) have been condensed with oxymethylenecamphors (*d*, *l* & *dl*). The rotatory power of the optically active isomerides (*d* and *l*) is found to be identical and can be expressed by the simple dispersion equation of Drude, $[\alpha] = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$.

The replacement of a hydrogen atom by a negative group such as hydroxyl diminishes the rotation. The effect of substitution on optical activity is represented by a series which agrees, subject to minor variations, with the *polar* one. The acetylation of the hydroxyl group reduces the rotation of the parent compound. The fall in rotatory power is remarkably great on benzylation. The influence of solvent as well as that of position isomerism on optical rotatory power is also discussed.

In this communication we present further experimental data on the rotatory dispersion of the condensation products of oxymethylenecamphors (*d*, *l* and *dl*) with aminophenols (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) and their acetylated and benzyolated derivatives.

The condensation products of oxymethylenecamphors (*d*, *l*, and *dl*) with *p*-aminophenol are difficult to crystallise.

The Influence of Chemical Constitution on the Character of Rotatory Dispersion.—According to the electrostatic modification of Thomson's rule (*Phil. Mag.*, 1923, 46, 497) as suggested by Rule (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1121), there is a close relation between the optical rotation of a compound and the electrochemical nature of the substituent groups. The introduction of an electronegative group such as hydroxyl would result in a decrease of the optical rotation of the parent compound. This is corroborated by our experimental results (Table A).

On a careful study of the rotatory power data for the substituted anilinomethylenecamphors (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) in different solvents given in Table A, we find that among the position isomerides the influence of substituents on rotatory power is as follows :

For the *ortho* compounds, H>OH>Cl>Br in all solvents.

For the *meta* compounds, H>CH₃>OH>Cl>Br > I in 3 solvents ;
and H>OH>CH₃>Cl>Br > I in 2 solvents.

For the *para* compounds, H>OH>CH₃>Cl>Br > I in 4 solvents.

The position of the hydroxyl group (OH) in the polar series is not known with certainty.

The specific inductive capacity on non-polar compounds of the type C₆H₅X arranges in the following sequence :—NO₂>CN>COMe>CHO>Cl>OH>NH₂>Br > N(Me)₂>OMe>Et>H (Landolt), although for phenol it is not strictly comparable as it has been determined at 48° and not at the ordinary temperature as

with other compounds. The dissociation constant of substituted benzoic acids arranges in the order :— $\text{NO}_2 > \text{COOH} > \text{Br} > \text{Cl} > \text{OH} > \text{Me} > \text{OMe} > \text{H} > \text{NH}_2 > \text{NMe}_2$ (Landolt). This agrees well with the series obtained experimentally from optical rotation subject to minor variations as stated above ; the position of Me and OH groups often inrrechanging between themselves.

The Influence of Substituents on Rotatory Power of the Position Isomerides.—The sequence of rotatory power of the position isomerides of the hydroxy compound (Table A) is $\text{un} > \textit{p} > \textit{o} > \textit{m}$ in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone and pyridine, but $\text{un} > \textit{p} > \textit{m} > \textit{o}$ in chloroform. In the case of the acetoxy derivatives, the sequence of decreasing rotatory power in ethyl alcohol is $\text{un} > \textit{o} > \textit{p} > \textit{m}$. This is, however, neither in agreement with Frankland's lever arm hypothesis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 1583) nor with the electrostatic modification as suggested by Rule (*loc. cit.*), as the unsubstituted compound has always the highest rotatory power in all these cases. This point has already been emphasised in previous communications (Singh, Mallick and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 95 ; Singh, Bhaduri and Barat, *loc. cit.* Singh and Bhaduri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, A, 15, 283).

In the above discussion the comparison is confined to the green mercury line (A. U. 5461), but if it is made for the red lithium line (A. U. 6708), the order of position isomerides is changed ; for example in methyl alcohol, it is $\text{un} > \textit{p} > \textit{m} > \textit{o}$; the *o*- and *m*- isomerides interchanging. In order to overcome this difficulty in compounds which show simple dispersion, *i.e.* obey the one-term Drude equation, $[\alpha] = \frac{K_0}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$, the values of K_0 (the absolute rotation) may be compared. These values are for λ (where $\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2 = 1$) always in the infra-red region beyond 10,000 A. U. and are independent of the wave-length. The values of K_0 , given in the tables (I to VI & A) do not also support the above mentioned rules regarding the order of rotatory power of the position isomerides.

Effect of Acetylation and Benzoylation.—Rule (*loc. cit.*) anticipated that the substitution of a hydroxylic hydrogen atom by a negative alkyl or a positive benzoyl group would influence the rotation in opposite direction. Frankland and Carter (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2470) have shown that the introduction of the benzoyl group alters the rotation of amyl alcohol from $-3'87^\circ$ to $+9'52^\circ$ and it is thus equivalent to an increase in positive rotation. But Singh and Bhaduri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 550) have, however, shown that the acetyl derivative of *p*-phenylenebisamino-*d*-camphor has much lower rotation than the parent compound. Our present experiments also show that the rotatory power of the acetoxy derivatives of anilinomethylenecamphors is lower than that of the parent hydroxy derivatives (*vide* Tables I—VI).

The benzoyl derivative has still a remarkably lower rotation (Table VII). These facts are against Thomson's generalisation and may be illustrated from the values of $[\alpha]_{5461}^{25}$ in ethyl alcohol :—

<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor,	450'5"
<i>p</i> -Acetoxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor,	190'3"
<i>p</i> -Benzoxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor,	6'2"

The Effect of the Nature of Solvent on Rotatory Power.—The specific rotatory power for Hg_{green} line of the compounds in different solvents is given in Table A. It is found that the order of increasing rotatory power is methyl alcohol > ethyl alcohol > acetone > pyridine and chloroform. The positions of chloroform and pyridine are, however, frequently interchanging which is approximately in the order of the dielectric constant of the solvents.

TABLE A.
[α]_{D²⁵}Hg_{green} for the *dextro* isomerides.

Formula of the substance	MeOH.	EtOH.	Me ₂ CO.	Pyridine.	CHCl ₃ .
* R. C ₈ H ₈ ...	480.0° (86.8)	451.3° (83.1)	448.9° (81.2)	433.2° (81.2)	424.6° (78.6)
* R. C ₈ H ₈ . Me (<i>m</i> -) ...	454.4 (85.2)	439.9 (81.0)	442.3 (82.3)	405.8 (80.5)	384.8 (68.6)
* R. C ₈ H ₈ . Me (<i>p</i> -) ...	465.0 (79.6)	440.8 (80.1)	425.8 (78.8)	401.6 (74.1)	401.6 (74.1)
** R. C ₈ H ₈ Cl (<i>o</i> -) ...	400.2 (64.8)	405.8 (72.2)	380.0 (61.4)	391.3 (63.7)	386.0 (61.8)
** " (<i>m</i> -) ...	388.5 (63.1)	384.7 (62.5)	389.0 (63.7)	374.4 (63.7)	381.4 (61.2)
** " (<i>p</i> -) ...	417.7 (75.3)	406.3 (73.2)	401.8 (70.6)	394.4 (68.2)	374.6 (67.6)
** R. C ₈ H ₈ Br (<i>o</i> -) ...	347.5 (53.7)	339.9 (55.1)	330.1 (54.1)	328.4 (51.9)	329.0 (51.8)
** " (<i>m</i> -) ...	...	354.0 (63.5)	348.4 (64.7)	334.3 (59.2)	324.1 (56.7)
** " (<i>p</i> -) ...	361.1 (63.7)	355.6 (62.4)	360.6 (65.3)	348.8 (53.6)	324.3 (57.3)
** R. C ₈ H ₈ I (<i>m</i> -) ...	328.5 (60.4)	319.5 (58.5)	309.7 (57.6)	294.8 (53.6)	279.1 (51.1)
** " (<i>p</i> -) ...	338.1 (59.0)	325.9 (54.3)	326.5 (55.2)	318.4 (54.9)	300.9' (51.5)
R. C ₈ H ₈ · OH (<i>o</i> -) ...	437.5 (75.1)	436.2 (74.6)	419.6 (79.0)	413.3 (68.5)	409.8 (66.5)
" (<i>m</i> -) ...	435.4 (78.5)	417.1 (82.8)	412.6 (79.5)	410.5 (80.1)	389.5 (77.0)
" (<i>p</i> -) ...	456.5 (83.1)	450.5 (80.8)	430.0 (74.7)	426.2 (73.5)	418.0 (76.5)
R. C ₈ H ₈ O · OC. Me (<i>o</i> -) ...	...	261.8 (53.3)	254.3 ...	...	266.3 (47.2)
" (<i>m</i> -) ...	189.1 (42.2)	181.1 (40.4)	180.9 (32.2)	...	...
" (<i>p</i> -) ...	202.2 (39.2)	190.3 (38.6)	...	180.9 (41.8)	...

* Singh, Bhaduri and Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 345.

** Singh and Bhaduri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, A, 6, 341; 1939, 10, 359. R = C₈H₁₄ $\begin{matrix} \diagup \text{C} = \text{CH} \cdot \text{NH} - \\ | \\ \text{CO} \end{matrix}$

(a) Figures within brackets refer to the numerical value of K_D of the Drude equation, $\frac{K_D}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$, referred to on p. 3 for λ , when $\lambda = \sqrt{\lambda_0^2 + \lambda^2}$.

The rotatory dispersion of these compounds is found, as with other compounds of the series (Singh and Badhuri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 771; 1931, 8, 181, 625, 623; Singh, Bhaduri and Barat, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 345) to obey the simple dispersion equation of Drude, $[\alpha] = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$. But *p*-benzoxypheylaminomethylenecamphor does not, however, obey this one term formula: the plot of $1/\alpha$ against λ^2 is not a straight line, but a steep curve. It, therefore, exhibits *complex* dispersion.

The Physical Identity of Enantiomers.—According to Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry, the *d*- and *l*-forms are represented as true mirror images of one another differing in sign but absolutely identical in the numerical value of the rotatory power. The numerical values of the rotatory power of the two forms (Table I—VI) are identical within the limit of experimental errors. Out of 200 observations now recorded, in as many as 125 cases, the difference in the numerical values of specific rotatory power of the opposite isomers corresponds to a difference of less than 0.01° in the observed angle of rotation and in 72 other cases the corresponding angle lies between 0.01° and 0.02°, which is the limit of experimental error allowable in such measurements. Only in the remaining cases, *viz.* *m*-hydroxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in pyridine for Ag_{52.00} (Table II) and *p*-acetoxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in pyridine for Hg_{54.00} (Table VI), the difference corresponds to between 0.02° and 0.03° in the observed angle of rotation. These, however, are of the nature of casual experimental errors.

Whether a racemic form is a *dl*-compound of the *d*- and *l*-isomers can be sometimes inferred from the melting point determinations*. Three cases arise: (a) The melting point of the racemic form is higher than that of the active forms, in which case it is a true *dl*-compound at least in the solid state. The racemic form of *o*-acetoxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor is an instance of this nature. (b) The melting point of the racemic form is lower than that of the active forms, as in the case of *o*-hydroxy- and *p*-hydroxyphenylaminomethylenecamphors. In this case for the characterisation of the racemic modification, the preparation of its freezing point-composition curve with the corresponding *d*- or *l*-form will be necessary. (c) The melting point of the racemic form is identical with that of the active forms as in the case of *m*-hydroxy- and *m*-acetoxyphenylaminomethylenecamphors. Some more examples of the racemic form having identical melting points with those of the active forms have been already cited (Singh and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 623; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, A, 15, 282). In this case, as in the first, the racemic modification is a *dl*-compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of o-, m- and p-Hydroxyphenylaminomethylene-d-camphor.—Oxymethylene-*d*-camphor (1 mol.) in methyl alcoholic solution was added to the acetic acid solution of *o*-, *m*- or *p*-aminophenol (1 mol.) and kept for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The mixture was then poured into water and the colourless product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol. The condensation products of oxymethylenecamphors (*d*-, *l*- and *dl*-) with *p*-aminophenol were difficult and slow to crystallise. On

* This will not characterise a racemic solid solution.

keeping the dilute alcoholic solution of the crude products for 10 to 15 days, they were obtained as rectangular blocks.

Acetyl derivatives of the above compounds were prepared by warming the hydroxy compounds with acetyl chloride on the water-bath for about hour. The reaction mixture was poured into water; an oil separated which solidified on stirring with sodium carbonate. The solid mass, thus obtained, was crystallised from dilute alcohol. The laevo and racemic forms were prepared in the same way.

The melting points, time of crystallisation and analytical data are tabulated below.

TABLE B.

Hydroxy- and acetoxy-phenylaminomethylenecamphors.

		Hydroxy compounds.					Acetoxy compounds. Colourless needles. Time of crystallisation, 15-20 days.					
		M.p.	Appearance.	Time of crystallisation.	Analysis (found %)			M.p.	Analysis (found %)			
					C.	H.	N.		C.	H.	N.	
<i>ortho</i>	<i>d</i>	180-182°	Colourless needles.	3-4 hours	75.1	7.75	—	<i>d</i>	131-32°	72.6	8.0	—
	<i>l</i>	"	"	"	75.2	7.87	—	<i>l</i>	"	—	—	4.54
	<i>r</i>	164-65	"	"	75.1	7.80	—	<i>r</i>	140-42	—	—	4.58
<i>meta</i>	<i>d</i>	165	"	3-4 days	75.1	7.55	5.16	<i>d</i>	140-42	—	—	4.54
	<i>l</i>	"	"	"	75.1	7.7	5.4	<i>l</i>	"	72.99	7.6	—
	<i>r</i>	"	"	"	—	—	5.49	<i>r</i>	"	—	—	—
<i>para</i>	<i>d</i>	158-60	Yellowish rectangles	15-20 days	74.7	7.72	—	<i>d</i>	220-22	73.1	7.5	4.52
	<i>l</i>	"	"	"	75.5	7.9	—	<i>l</i>	"	72.99	7.6	—
	<i>r</i>	150-52	"	"	—	—	5.57	<i>r</i>	195-97	—	—	4.70
C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₃ N requires					75.27	7.74	5.43	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₃ N requires 73.18 7.35 4.47				

p-Benzoxyphenylaminomethylene-*d*-camphor was prepared by shaking the *p*-hydroxy compound with benzoyl chloride and excess of sodium hydroxide for 2 hours. The oily substance, thus obtained, was crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 236-37°. (Found: N, 3.73. C₂₄H₂₅O₃N requires N, 3.82 per cent).

The compound is soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol, ether, chloroform, acetone and sparingly so in benzene.

The benzoyl derivatives of *o*- and *m*-hydroxy compounds are oils which refused to solidify.

The rotatory power determinations were made in a 2-d cm. jacketted tube at 35°. The value of λ_0 , calculated from the dispersion formula, is given in the following tables and is expressed as $\cdot 1$ or 10^{-4} cm.

TABLE I.
o-Hydroxyphenylaminomethylbornecamphors.

Line.	Solvent:		Ethyl alcohol.		Methyl alcohol.		Acetone.		Pyridine.		Chloroform.	
	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d \\ l \end{array} \right\}$	0.4024 0.4000	0.4000 0.4016	0.4028 0.4028	0.4000 0.4016	0.4028 0.4028	0.4000 0.4016	0.3992 0.4020	0.3992 0.4020	0.3672 0.4012	0.3672 0.4012
Calculated			$\pm \frac{74.65}{\lambda^2} - 0.1270$	$\pm \frac{75.10}{\lambda^2} - 0.1261$	$\pm \frac{79.05}{\lambda^2} - 0.1048$	$\pm \frac{68.53}{\lambda^2} - 0.1320$	$\pm \frac{66.51}{\lambda^2} - 0.1399$					
			0.3564	0.3552	0.3238	0.3634	0.3741					
			Obs. [α]	Obs. [α]	Obs. [α]	Obs. [α]	Obs. [α]	Obs. [α]				
			d	l	d	l	d	l	d	l	d	l
Cd _{50.5}			+566.8°	-567.5°	+514.0°	-565.4°	+542.6°	-541.2°	+561.0°	-560.9°	+561.0°	-560.9°
Ag _{50.0}			517.0	517.5	475.5	515.5	492.9	491.3	506.4	506.0	506.4	506.0
Hg _{50.0}			436.2	436.2	409.8	436.9	413.3	411.8	419.6	420.1	419.6	420.1
Hg _{55.0}			360.4	360.7	343.9	361.1	339.5	339.8	343.1	342.8	343.1	342.8
N _{50.0}			339.2	339.8	327.8	339.9	317.3	318.7	320.1	320.4	320.1	320.4
Li _{10.0}			304.5	304.3	295.5	305.1	279.0	278.7	285.9	286.6	285.9	286.6
Cd _{50.0}			259.7	259.8	254.6	259.0	243.0	242.6	242.4	243.1	242.4	243.1
Li _{5.0}			231.1	231.3	229.7	231.6	215.3	216.4	213.9	214.4	213.9	214.4
			No mutarotation.	No mutarotation.	No mutarotation.	No mutarotation.	No mutarotation.	No mutarotation.				

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TABLE III.

p-Hydroxyphenylaminoethylbenzenesulphates.

Conc. (g/100 c.c.)	Solvent:		Methyl alcohol.	Acetone	Pyridine.	Chloroform.
	Ethyl alcohol.					
	d		0.4020	0.3984	0.4000	0.4008
	l		0.4004	0.3992	0.4008	0.4000
Calc.	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$		$\frac{83.10}{\lambda^2 - 0.1164}$	$\frac{74.70}{\lambda^2 - 0.1214}$	$\frac{73.63}{\lambda^2 - 0.1346}$	$\frac{76.47}{\lambda^2 - 0.1161}$
	λ_0		0.3413	0.3485	0.3572	0.3408
Line.	Obs. $[\alpha]$		Obs. $[\alpha]$	Obs. $[\alpha]$	Obs. $[\alpha]$	Obs. $[\alpha]$
C_{6450}	d	l	d	l	d	l
	+581.3°	-581.3°	+587.1°	-588.1°	+553.8°	-552.8°
A_{6150}	532.5	532.5	536.1	535.8	509.0	507.3
H_{6600}	452.5	450.0	456.5	457.1	430.0	428.4
H_{6700}	378.5	378.5	381.6	381.0	354.8	354.5
N_{6100}	356.2	355.0	360.7	360.9	336.0	337.0
L_{6100}	318.7	318.7	325.4	326.0	300.9	301.8
C_{6450}	273.7	275.0	280.0	279.7	257.3	258.1
L_{6700}	245.0	243.8	250.0	248.5	...	...
	No mutarotation	No mutarotation	No mutarotation	No mutarotation	No mutarotation	No mutarotation.

TABLE IV.

o-Acetoxyphenylaminomethylenecamphors

Solvent :	Ethyl alcohol.		Methyl alcohol.		Acetone.	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	<i>d</i>	0.4000		0.4004		0.4012
	<i>l</i>	0.4000		0.4028		0.4016
Calc.	[α]	$\pm \frac{47.20}{\lambda^2 - 0.1213}$		$\pm \frac{53.30}{\lambda^2 - 0.0971}$		$\pm \frac{45.26}{\lambda^2 - 0.1201}$
	λ^0	0.3484		0.3117		0.3466
Line.	Obs. [α]		Obs. [α]		Obs. [α]	
	<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>
Cd ₅₀₀₀	...	...	+330.9°	-330.3°	+326.6°	-326.2°
Ag ₅₂₀₀	...	...	...	...	299.1	300.1
Hg ₅₄₀₀	+266.3°	-267.8°	264.8	264.5	254.3	255.3
Hg ₅₇₀₀	221.3	221.3	224.6	224.6	211.9	211.6
Na ₅₈₀₀	208.7	207.5	212.3	213.5	199.4	199.2
Li ₆₁₀₀	187.9	187.5	193.5	194.9	179.4	178.1
Cd ₆₄₀₀	161.2	161.2	...	...	...	...
Li ₆₇₀₀	143.3	145.0	151.0	151.6	137.1	137.0

TABLE V.

m-Acetoxyphenylaminomethylenecamphors.

Solvent :	Ethyl alcohol.		Methyl alcohol.		Acetone.	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	<i>d</i>	0.4024		0.4024		0.4008
	<i>l</i>	0.4004		0.4000		0.4004
Calc.	[α]	$\pm \frac{40.38}{\lambda^2 - 0.0748}$		$\pm \frac{42.25}{\lambda^2 - 0.0748}$		$\pm \frac{32.15}{\lambda^2 - 0.1193}$
	λ^0	0.2735		0.2735		0.3454
Line.	Obs. [α]		Obs. [α]		Obs. [α]	
	<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>
Cd ₅₀₀₀	+220.0°	-220.0°	+228.2°	-228.3°	...	...
Ag ₅₂₀₀	205.1	204.4	215.2	215.0	...	...
Hg ₅₄₀₀	181.1	181.1	189.1	189.1	+190.9°	-182.3°
Hg ₅₇₀₀	155.4	154.7	163.0	162.5	149.7	149.8
Na ₅₈₀₀	146.6	147.5	155.5	155.0	141.0	141.1
Li ₆₁₀₀	135.2	136.3	143.1	142.5	127.3	126.2
Cd ₆₄₀₀	119.4	117.5	124.4	123.0	...	...
Li ₆₇₀₀	108.1	107.4	113.1	113.7	97.1	97.4
	No mutarotation.		No mutarotation.		No mutarotation.	

TABLE VI.
p-Acetoxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor.

Solvent :		Ethyl alcohol.		Methyl alcohol.		Pyridine.		
Conc. (g./100 c. c.)	{	<i>d</i>	0.4020		0.4008		0.4036	
		<i>l</i>	0.4016		0.4004		0.4004	
Calc.	{	[α]	$\pm \frac{38.58}{\lambda^2 - 0.0958}$		$\pm \frac{39.23}{\lambda^2 - 0.1040}$		$\pm \frac{41.75}{\lambda^2 - 0.0682}$	
		λ_0	0.3095		0.3225		0.2573	
Line		Obs. [α]		Obs. [α]		Obs. []		
		<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>l</i>	
Cd ₁₀₀₀	—	...	+236.9°	-235.3°	...	...	+216.9°	-216.0°
Ag ₅₂₀₀	...	...	...	...	...	...	204.5	204.4
Hg ₅₄₀₀	...	...	190.3	190.5	+202.1°	-202.4°	180.9	182.3
Hg ₅₇₁₀	...	...	162.9	161.9	172.2	172.4	154.4	153.6
Na ₅₈₀₀	...	...	153.0	153.6	161.0	159.8	148.8	148.6
Li ₁₁₀₀	...	...	139.3	138.2	146.0	144.9	136.4	134.9
Cd ₆₃₀	—	...	120.7	120.8	...	...	...	...
Li ₉₁₀	—	...	112.0	112.1	113.6	112.4	...	...

No mutarotation

TABLE VII.

p-Benzoxyphenylaminomethylene-d-camphor in ethyl alcohol.

Line.	α.		[α].	
Cd ₅₀₀₀	...	0.06°	...	7.37°
Hg ₅₁₀₀	...	0.05	...	6.20
Hg ₅₇₀₀	...	0.03	...	4.33
Na ₅₁₀₀	...	0.02	...	2.48

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